

Studies on the Kinetics of the Decomposition of the Chloro-complex of Cerium(IV) in Sulphuric Acid Medium

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The reaction between cerium(IV) and chloride ion proceeds through the initial formation of a red-coloured complex which is unstable and decomposes gradually. The kinetics of the decomposition reaction obeys the first-order law. The activation energy calculated is 19.35 kcal./mole. H_2SO_4 retards the rate of the decomposition of the complex.

The use of acidified solutions of cerium(IV) as volumetric reagents, as suggested by Lango¹ and Job², was later studied by Willard and Young³. Furman⁴ and Atanasius⁵ also described various potentiometric methods using cerium(IV) sulphate as titrant. Smith and Getz⁶ from oxidation potential data concluded that cerium(IV) ion formed complexes with some inorganic anions, e.g., chloride, sulphate, and nitrate. King and Pandow⁷ showed that cerium(IV) ion formed no complex in perchloric acid solution. Hardwick and Robertson⁸ calculated the equilibrium ratios (constants) on the formation of $Ce(OH)^{3+}$ from cerium(IV) and the dimer $(Ce-O-Ce)^{6+}$ from $Ce(OH)^{3+}$ in cerium(IV) perchlorate solution from spectral studies. The same authors also calculated from spectral study the formation constant of the cerium(IV) sulphate complex. Duke and Borchers⁹ have suggested that oxidation of chloride ion by Ce(IV) ion proceeds, resulting chiefly through the production of chlorine. They investigated the kinetics in presence of thallium and found the overall reaction to be of the zero order.

The present communication deals with the kinetics of the decomposition of the red-coloured chloro-complex of cerium(IV), when the concentration of HCl is very high (above 3*N*).

EXPERIMENTAL

A solution of ceric ammonium sulphate of G.R. (E. Merck) quality was prepared in H_2SO_4 of A.R. quality. Ceric sulphate solution was standardised by iodometric method. A stock ceric sulphate solution in 2*N*- H_2SO_4 was employed. HCl used was of AnalaR quality.

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2. *Compt. rend.*, 1899, **101**, 128.
3. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, **50**, 1322; 1929, **51**, 139.
4. *Ibid.*, 1928, **50**, 755.
5. *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1927, **30**, 73.
6. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1938, **10**, 141.
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Since the decomposition of the cerium(IV) complex is rapid, observation in a spectrophotometer is not practicable. Measurements in a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter were made throughout the experiments.

The colour of the complex being red, to obtain appreciable absorption green filters having wave length range between 520 $\mu\mu$ and 580 $\mu\mu$ were used.

Optical Density.—The optical density of the complex at zero time could not be measured accurately as it decomposed as soon as it was formed. In practice, in all the experiments 2 ml of ceric sulphate solution was mixed with an equal volume of HCl of desired concentration in colorimetric test tubes and the optical densities were followed.

Order of the Reaction.—The order of the decomposition reaction of the complex was determined at three different concentrations of HCl, viz., 6 *N*, 5 *N*, and 4 *N*. The concentration of cerium(IV) sulphate solution used was *M*/10 (exact). The change in optical density was followed in the colorimeter with time and the plot of the logarithm of the concentration of the complex, i.e., $\log\{(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0\}$ against time [where, $(O.D.)_t$ and $(O.D.)_0$ are the optical densities of the mixture at any time *t* and of the doubly diluted parent cerium(IV) sulphate solution respectively] yields a straight line. This indicates that the reaction is a first-order one with respect to the coloured complex (Fig. 1.) From the slopes of the linear plots, the values of the velocity constants have been calculated.

FIG. 1

Effect of H_2SO_4 .—Decomposition of the complex was retarded by H_2SO_4 . The plot $\log K$ against $\log [H^+]$ with respect to H_2SO_4 yields a straight line. The values of *K* and $[H^+]$ are shown in Table I and also in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively. It should be mentioned here that for the study of the effect of H_2SO_4 , the final strength of HCl was maintained at 4 *N*.

Effect of Dilution.—The rate constants were also determined at different concentrations of the reactants. The concentration of ceric sulphate solution used for this purpose was $M/20$ (exact), obtained by diluting $M/10$ (exact) ceric sulphate with an equal volume of $1 N-H_2SO_4$; the concentrations of HCl in the final solution were $6 N$, $5 N$, and $4 N$ respectively. Although the values of the rate constants (vide Table II) obtained at these three acid concentrations were nearly the same, the progressive decrease was found with decrease in the concentration of HCl.

TABLE I
Ceric sulphate = $M/20$. HCl = $4 N$. Temp. = 34° .

[H ⁺] in H ₂ SO ₄ .	Log [H ⁺].	K (min ⁻¹) × 10.	Log K.
0.9863	1.9939	7.461	1.8728
1.7050	0.2316	3.454	1.5384
2.1540	0.3332	1.520	1.1818
3.1420	0.4972	1.105	1.0435

TABLE II
Ceric sulphate = $M/40$. Temp. = 34° .

Conc. of HCl	..	6N	5N	4N
K (min ⁻¹ × 10)	..	1.256	1.128	1.057

TABLE III

Ceric of sulphate = $M/20$. HCl = $4N$.

Temp. (in Abs.)	k (min^{-1}) $\times 10$.	Log k .	$1/T \times 10^4$.
307°	1.696	1.2296	32.57
300°	0.859	2.8192	33.33
293°	0.329	2.5172	34.13

Effect of Temperature.—The velocity constants were determined at three different temperatures, viz., 34°, 27°, and 20°. All these experiments were performed at identical H^+ ion concentration and log k was then plotted against $1/T$. From the linear plot, the activation energy was calculated (vide Fig. 4 and Table III). The activation energy is found to be 19.35 kcal./mole.

FIG. 4

FIG. 3

DISCUSSION

For the kinetic study, the optical density is followed with time and change in the optical density, i.e., $(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0 \propto (a-x)$ is worked out in the following way:

The ceric sulphate solution has got a definite amount of absorption. When mixed with an equal volume of HCl (conc.), a deep-red coloured solution is formed, the colour of

which disappears soon with restoration of the original colour of the solution, which again in course of time goes off due to formation of cerium (III) salt. Since the increase in optical density from the initial value (half diluted ceric sulphate solution) is due to formation of the complex only, the concentration of the complex at any instant is simply the difference between the optical density of the red-coloured complex $(O.D.)_t$ and the optical density of the half diluted ceric sulphate solution $(O.D.)_0$. Therefore, the disappearance of the red-coloured complex and its concentration is characterised by the value of the optical density and $\log (\text{complex}) \propto \log \{(O.D.)_t - (O.D.)_0\}$.

It is also found that with the decrease of hydrochloric acid concentration, the slopes remain the same, but the intercepts are in the order of diminishing sequence. This infers that the amount of complex formation is greater with higher HCl concentration, but the reaction rate at a constant temperature is independent of the acid concentration.

With the increase in H_2SO_4 concentration, the reaction rate is found to diminish and the retardation is probably due to the inhibiting action of SO_4^{2-} ions. On the other hand, addition of an acid other than H_2SO_4 , *i.e.* HNO_3 , produces an insignificant retardation. The increase in the concentration of H_2SO_4 causes the rate to be decreased ($K = 1.696 \times 10^{-1}$ to $1.057 \times 10^{-1} \text{ min}^{-1}$). This is also evident from our experiments with half diluted ceric sulphate solution (dilution was carried out in 1N- H_2SO_4) and HCl.

The activation energy (E) of the decomposition reaction of the complex, calculated by plotting $\log K$ against $1/T$, is found to be 19.35 kcal./mole. We have observed that the activation energy of the decomposition of chloro-complex, obtained by the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid in cerium (IV) perchlorate solution (results unpublished) is 6.31 kcal./mole. In comparison to this value, activation energy in the case of cerium (IV) sulphate is much higher (about 3 times). This is because of the much faster decomposition of the complex in perchloric acid medium than that in the sulphuric acid medium.

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